

Decentring the Study of Migrant
Returns and Return Policies

Country Dossier Iraq

Return migration governance in the African and Middle Eastern regions and the role of the EU

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List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Meaning
CSOs	Civil Society Organizations
ETTC	European Technology and Training Centre
EU	European Union
GCM	Global Compact for Migration
HHRO	Hammurabi Human Rights Organization
HTS	Hay'at Tahrir al-Sham
ICMPD	International Center for Migration Policy Development
INIS	Iraqi National Intelligence Service
INSS	Iraqi National Security Service
IOM	International Organization for Migration
ISIS	Islamic State of Iraq and the Levant
JCC	Joint Crisis Coordination Center
KRG	Kurdistan Regional Government
KRI	Kurdistan Region of Iraq
MOFA	Ministry of Foreign Affairs
MOI	Ministry of Interior
MOMD	Ministry of Migration and Displacement
MOP	Ministry of Planning
MOLSA	Ministry of Labor and Social Affairs
NGOs	Non-Governmental Organizations
SDF	Syrian Democratic Forces
UN	United Nations
UNHCR	United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees

1. Summary

This report examines a specific instance of South-to-South migration: the return of Syrian refugees to their homeland, Syria – after the relative stability in the country and the cessation of military operations and conflicts. By focusing on the dynamics of return, the conditions both in sending and receiving countries, as well as opportunities and challenges associated with return and reintegration, this study aims to contribute to a broader understanding of the complex dynamics of return migration in the Global South. The report also reveals the extent of consistency in policies, programs and practices at the various local, regional and international levels in both Iraq and Syria, and the extent of their adaptation and compatibility with the constitution in the two countries, as well as with the rules of international law regarding the conditions for providing the necessary protection and respecting human rights standards.

The report reviews the situation of Syrians in Iraq, the reasons and motives that led to their asylum in Iraq, their social, economic and political circumstances, as well as the challenges they face regarding their arrival, reception and livelihoods. It further sheds light on the characteristics of the management of return migration from Iraq to Syria, its nature and type, the main actors involved, the policies and practices followed, the coordination between different levels, the extent of these policies' response to the country's social and political needs, along with the level of their integration or intersection with each other. The report therefore explores the governance of return migration at local and national/federal levels, and aims to understand the influence of European Union (EU) policies in shaping policy outcomes.

Furthermore, based on field meetings and interviews the report presents perceptions and experiences of different actors involved in return operations, experts, policymakers and policy implementers, as well as representatives of national and international organizations, and beneficiaries concerning return migration. It also analyzes the governmental response level in the two countries, Iraq and Syria, to return migration at the level of strategies, plans, programs, policies and practices. The report further identifies several key obstacles and challenges, providing policy recommendations for the development of a return policy which ensures a dignified, safe, regular and orderly return.

GAPs Project

GAPs is a Horizon Europe project that aims to conduct a comprehensive multidisciplinary study on the drivers of return policies and the barriers and enablers of international cooperation on return migration. The overall aim of the project is to examine the disconnects and discrepancies between expectations of return policies and their actual outcomes by de-centring the dominant, one-sided understanding of “return policymaking.” To this end, GAPs:

- examine the shortcomings of EU’s return governance;
- analyse enablers and barriers to international cooperation, and
- explore the perspectives of migrants themselves to understand their knowledge, aspirations and experiences with return policies.

GAPs combines its decentring approach with three innovative concepts:

- a focus on return migration infrastructures, which allows the project to analyse governance fissures;
- an analysis of return migration diplomacy to understand how relations between EU Member States and with third countries hinder cooperation on return; and
- a trajectory approach that uses a socio-spatial and temporal lens to understand migrant agency.

GAPs is an interdisciplinary 3-year project (2023-2026), co-coordinated by Uppsala University and the Bonn International Centre for Conflict Studies with 17 partners in 12 countries on 4 continents. 1-GAPs’ fieldwork has been conducted in 14 countries: Jordan, Lebanon, Sweden, Nigeria, Germany, Morocco, the Netherlands, Afghanistan, Poland, Georgia, Turkey, Tunisia, Greece and Iraq.

This country dossier has been compiled in the context of the GAPs Work Package on ‘Return Migration Governance in the African and Middle Eastern Regions and the Role of the EU.’

Since the vast majority of migrants and refugees move and reside in and among countries in the immediate region of their origin countries, return migration will also predominantly take place within the region of countries in crisis. Yet, scholarly concerns have overwhelmingly focused on the minority of migrants who travelled further afield, in particular to the European Union, and return from there to their regions of origin. Relatively little attention has been given to return policies of neighbouring receiving states in the Global South.

Disregarding this regional dimension puts a Eurocentric bias on the study of return migration governance. Regional return governance, moreover, both shapes and is shaped by the externalization and return migration policies of the EU. On the one hand, the EU’s deterrence and externalization ‘partnerships’ fundamentally affect return diplomacies, infrastructures, and trajectories in its neighbouring regions. On the other hand, the governance of regional returns has repercussions the migration dynamics the EU seeks to control, for its engagement with ‘third countries,’ and for the international norms it claims to uphold.

To address this knowledge gap, therefore, this Work Package has the aim to better understand the intersections between (i) return migration governance within the African and Middle Eastern regions and (ii) the role of the European Union and its external migration policy. To this end, it asks three core research questions: (i) What characterizes return migration governance within African and Middle Eastern regions? Specifically: how are these modalities shaped by the EU’s

external migration policy?; (ii) What are the driving forces behind these types of return migration governance? Specifically: how are these drivers affected by the EU's external migration policy?; and (iii) What are the effects of these drivers and modalities of regional migration governance, for both people and policy? Specifically: what are the implications of specific regional return migration governance for the EU's external migration policy? The Work Package answers these questions for eight 'host countries' (Iraq, Jordan, Lebanon, Türkiye, Iran, Morocco, Tunisia, Libya) focused on three 'origin countries' (Syria, Afghanistan, Nigeria).

Research in this Work Package is carried out in an embedded-multiple case study design, in which cases are selected for diversity (encompassing variation in return types) and representativeness (including main host countries in return systems that are salient to Europe, i.e., Africa, the broader Middle East). Data are generated through document analysis (a minimum of 20 documents – including academic papers, expert report, and media coverage – has been analyzed in-depth per country dossier) and 10 (semi-structured, in-depth) expert interviews (with state authorities, international organizations, and civil society actors) have been conducted. Data was coded iteratively. First deductively, through a common codebook based on a shared conceptual framework developed to answer the three core questions listed above. Particular attention here is paid to modalities (legal, policy and operational infrastructures), drivers (capacity and interests of actors), and outcomes (monitoring mechanisms and expert views on sustainability of returns). Second, data was coded inductively, highlighting emerging themes that were not included in the codebook but that nevertheless surfaced as contextually relevant. Research has been subject to ethical review of the host institutions of the individual researchers conducting the country-specific research. The core concern here has been to ensure (oral) informed consent for interviews on the basis of full anonymity of interlocutors. Document and interview analysis have been synthesized through two workshops dedicated to these specific research phases.

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William Warda

HHRO Team Main investigator

2. Introduction

Governance of migration is a major challenge for Iraq. There is still political disagreement between the ruling political blocs and groups that control political decisions on the issue of the return of migrants and refugees, coupled with Iraq's non-adherence to the 1951 Refugee Convention and its 1967 Protocol, in addition to the absence of a comprehensive law regulating the status of refugees in Iraq. This is because the current Iraqi law No. 51 of 1971 is concerned with refugees for political or military reasons only, without referring to the status of humanitarian asylum (Warda W. et al, 2018, p. 28). The main actors in this process, including the Ministry of Migration and Displacement (MOMD), the Ministry of Foreign Affairs (MOFA), the Ministry of Interior (MOI) and others, lack experience and expertise, and there is poor coordination among them. What is allocated to the MOMD as a major active ministry in this file does not meet the level of ambition, in light of the presence of large numbers of internally displaced persons, due to the violence that swept the country in recent years, in addition to the difficulties in obtaining accurate data on migrants in all their classifications, as well as the housing crisis (UNESCWA, 2019).

Iraq is striving to develop its capabilities in managing the issue of return migration and organizing the reality of migration and displaced persons in line with the principles of the Global Compact for Migration (GCM), which it was one of the first countries to join and the work of which it seeks to develop. The issue of return migration has faced major challenges in Iraq, perhaps not experienced by any other country, whether at the level of the return of Iraqi migrants to their country or the return of refugees present on its territory to their original homelands. Iraq has suffered severely from the ravages of wars over decades, the most recent of which was the war with the Islamic State of Iraq and the Levant (ISIS). Iraq is currently one of the countries most affected by environmental degradation and climate change, which adds other concerns that it may be an important driver of migration and an obstacle to the return of migrants. In the stage of stability, the end of conflict and the change in circumstances that led to migration, the voluntary return of refugees to their country has become necessary, provided that mechanisms for sustainable integration and means for safe and dignified return are provided.

Over the past few years, especially after Iraq signed the GCM on 19 December 2018, the country has demonstrated a clear commitment to implementing this Compact's provisions and adopting the application of its ten principles and 23 objectives (GCM, 2018). The migration data profile and migration governance indicators were evaluated, and a clear roadmap was drawn up through which a national framework for migration policy was established, culminating in the approval of the National Strategy for Migration Management, reflecting the government's approach to dealing with this important issue. This Strategy presents a comprehensive view of the depth and breadth of work covering legal affairs, migration data, return migration and economic affairs. In 2021, Iraq joined the initiative of countries supporting the GCM, which seeks to support the rights, dignity and well-being of migrants and returnees, believing in the need to address the causes of migration and ensure the rights of migrants, which are at the core of the Iraqi government's work (UN, 2022). As for the situation in Syria, the information provided in the report refers to the period prior to the change of the Syrian regime (the regime of Bashar al-Assad), as the writing of this report was about to be finalized when the regime change took place, as the current situation regarding return is drastically different that the country was not safe for the return of Syrians, especially after the crisis has worsened since 2011. Syrians have

additionally suffered from the difficulties of life inside and outside Syria because they have come to live in a state of continuous emergency, in light of the effects of poverty and harsh living conditions, as well as the devastating earthquakes that struck Turkey and northern Syria. The needs inside Syria, and among refugees in neighboring countries, are enormous since the Syrian refugee crisis is one of the largest displacement crises in the world. However, despite this, the matter no longer receives the necessary media attention, and funding levels are no longer commensurate with the growing volume of needs and requirements (Grande F., 2024).

The relative calm in some Syrian areas after the ceasefire decision on July 9, 2017, encouraged several Syrian refugees to attempt to return voluntarily, despite the presence of many obstacles and risks that hinder this process. Moreover, humanitarian organizations stated that the percentage of Syrian refugees who wish to return to the country voluntarily does not exceed 2% (The National News, 2024). In turn, the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR) policy does not encourage the return of refugees to their homelands, except after the security and humanitarian situation improves.

The past years of war in Syria have caused widespread and comprehensive destruction to the country's infrastructure, and the complete or partial destruction of most residential buildings, factories and farms, which has led to the tearing of the social fabric and the change of the demographic map due to internal displacement and migration (Syr-ASA-Micro-M). The problem of migration and displacement that has afflicted the Syrian people may be one of the biggest challenges that faced the government after the end of the conflict phase. Given the level of widespread and comprehensive conflict, and the inability to reach a state of peace in Syria, the current conditions are still not encouraging for voluntary return from neighboring countries on a large scale (Syria TV, 2023).

Syrians in Iraq receive great attention from the Iraqi community as well, as from the various Iraqi authorities. About 250,000 Syrians reside in Iraq, most of them in the Kurdistan Region of Iraq (KRI). About 38% of them reside in camps, while the remainder lives among host communities in urban areas. However, they face many challenges and problems in accessing work, housing, health and other life matters (Warda W., et al, 2018, p. 15). Their return to Syria is not an easy process in light of the complex requirements and procedures for travel, which require coordination between the parties involved in organizing the return process, as well as the presence of areas that are still unsafe and unstable in Syria, in addition to the need for advanced planning and large financial allocations to organize their return (HRW, 2024).

This research seeks to address the problem of Syrians residing in Iraq returning to their country and the challenges they face, in addition to identifying the driving forces behind the return process and its type. It also seeks to determine how these drivers are affected by Iraq's policies and the EU's external migration policies, and what the implications of regional return migration governance are on external migration policies, as well as the role of key actors in influencing the size and level of return.

This research will review the causes and motivations of Syrian migration to Iraq, along with the process of their arrival and reception in the country, determining their numbers and their economic, social and political conditions inside Iraq, as well as how Iraqi institutions deal with them. It will also examine the characteristics of return and governance in terms of its level and type, in addition to actors, policies and practices followed at the national and external levels. The research will address the impact of return governance on the level of protection for Syrians

in terms of international legislation and agreements, and the resulting consequences on the actual reality of return migration.

The issue of the voluntary return of Syrians from Iraq to Syria is receiving increasing international and regional attention, despite the weak performance of many active parties in facilitating the return migration process at this stage. This requires these parties to understand the requests and desires of these Syrians in the areas where they are located and to prepare to deal better with the voluntary return process, as the process of returning to Syria is not simple or easy. As such, it does not end with arranging travel procedures from the country of asylum to the home country (Syr-MNA-Micro-M). Rather, it is a difficult process with many complex procedures that require follow-up and coordination between all active parties, advanced planning and very large financial allocations (Özerdem A. and Sofizada A., 2006).

3. Methodology

This study relied on a combination of theoretical and practical sources to comprehensively cover all aspects of the topic. The methodology was therefore divided into two parts:

- 1- **Desk research:** Theoretical information was collected based on a comprehensive review of the available literature, reports and data of international organizations concerned with migration and the return issue, related research and studies, as well as data and statements issued by ministries and agencies specializing in return migration in both Iraq and Syria. Moreover, following up on media institutions, news agencies and related media reports, reports of human rights organizations concerned with the situation in Syria, official books, statistics, figures, as well as statements issued by the Iraqi MOMD, we tried to employ these in this study to reflect a more realistic and clearer picture.
- 2- **Field research and interviews:** Nine interviews were conducted with individual stakeholders in the context of fieldwork and at the meso level, in addition to holding an expanded roundtable meeting attended by representatives of relevant Iraqi ministries, international and national organizations, as well as interested activists. Moreover, meetings and conferences regarding migration and return were held during the research period. The research team benefited from these in order to obtain some answers that respond to the research requirements and enrich them. This is in addition to meetings and discussions with non-governmental organizations (NGOs) concerned with return and activists in the human rights field, as well as meeting with some returnees and other migrants. Seven individual interviews were conducted at the micro level with Syrian refugees residing in Iraq. In-depth interviews were conducted with them about their motivations for returning, the obstacles and challenges they face, as well as the reasons that prevent them from returning. These interviews were conducted in a safe environment, taking into account the participants' privacy and security by concealing their identities, while observing ethical standards in the process of asking questions and the confidentiality of the information obtained.

4. The situation of Syrians in Iraq

Iraq does not consider the Syrians arriving in its territory as refugees, but rather as guests. Therefore, asylum laws do not apply to them (Warda W. et al, 2020, p. 9; Dahi O., 2014). Iraq

relies on organizing the situation of asylum seekers and arrivals, as well as protecting them, by following the rules of international human rights law, especially since Iraq has joined and ratified eight out of nine agreements concerned with human rights (Warda et al, 2020, p. 11).

4.1. Drivers of migration from Syria to Iraq

There are several motives for migration in general, perhaps the most important of which are: political motives, security motives, climate change, poverty, persecution, study, marriage, seeking adventure, and others. In this context, however, we will discuss the real motives for the migration of Syrians from their country to Iraq, which are summarized in the following motives specific to the Syrian situation, after conducting interviews with many Syrians residing in Iraq who accurately indicated a set of main reasons that prompted them to leave Syria and head to Iraq. The most important of these reasons are:

- 1- **Political reasons:** A large portion of these Syrians indicated that there were political pressures imposed on them by the Syrian Government, represented by restricting their political and professional freedoms, and imposing a strict oligarchic dictatorship on society in general. There is no party pluralism, no political participation, no equal opportunities, as well as the spread of favoritism and nepotism. The larger Sunni Arab component there suffers from the bullying and encroachment of the ruling Alawite component in Syria, along with its practice of the most extreme types of marginalization and restrictions on participation in government (Jenkins B., 2014).
- 2- **Security reasons:** This is one of the most important objective reasons that prompted Syrians to emigrate, especially after the internal war that Syria has been experiencing since 2011, which has led to thousands of unarmed civilians being killed and the arrest of thousands of innocent citizens. This forced people to emigrate and stay away from conflict and war zones, in search of safer areas. Many of them chose to head to Iraq for multiple reasons, including geographical proximity, common history, as well as social and religious kinship. The Syrian migration journey to Iraq was not easy or simple, in particular for groups of young people and families residing in Syrian areas and governorates bordering Iraq. Rather, it may be better than other options available to them which are more expensive and dangerous, including migration to Europe via the Mediterranean Sea, or the complications of crossing to Turkey or Jordan. Statistics indicate that more than 8,000 migrants drowned in death boats crossing the Mediterranean Sea just in 2023, in addition to the possibility of some of them being arrested or imprisoned by authorities (Syr-SNF-Micro-M). The reason for the migration of about 14% of the world's immigrants is due to this. In addition, the security chaos that struck Syria due to the threats of terrorist organizations (Al-Qaeda, Jabhat al-Nusra, ISIS and others) has led to kidnappings, killings and destruction of infrastructure (Al-Shkara A., 2019).
- 3- **Economic reasons:** The most important of these are unemployment, poverty and difficult working conditions, as the internal war in Syria has destroyed the country's infrastructure. In addition, the economic blockade imposed on the country by the international community has negatively affected its economic situation. This was directly reflected in the lives of ordinary citizens, as the average employee's salary became no more than a few dollars per month. Moreover, the deterioration of the health and service sectors were directly linked to the economic situation, prompting many to resort to the option of migration, the search for

a safe haven and better living opportunities. One such country is Iraq, despite the unstable situation there due to the war with ISIS and the accompanying destruction of infrastructure in battle zones, in addition to the displacement of thousands of Iraqis outside their regions, besides the Iraqi Government's inability to secure necessities for these displaced persons on an ongoing and sufficient basis. We find that this situation did not prevent Syrian refugees from heading to Iraq to escape the war in their home country, the accompanying significant deterioration of the economic situation due to the siege imposed on it, the decline in the Syrian Lira's exchange rate as well as the crazy and continuous rise in food and fuel prices, with a margin of incitement to leave undertaken by opposition groups as international pressure cards (Hamdo A., 2020). It is estimated that about 15% of the total reasons for migration are due to aforementioned (Al-Shkara A., 2019).

- 4- **Persecution and restriction of freedoms:** There is a clear feeling among various segments of Syrian society, including religious or ethnic minorities, of persecution, discomfort and discrimination, which makes them feel as if they are low-level citizens. Some of those interviewed indicated that the ruling Alawite sect in Syria controls most of the state's functions and all senior government positions, especially security, intelligence and military ones. This, in turn, can forcibly extend its influence and control over the whole of society, preventing any political or social activity that would allow others to emerge or work. Consequently, this matter would weaken the sense of belonging and citizenship, pushing political and human rights activists to emigrate outside of Syria in order to exercise their freedom and pressure the Syrian Government from abroad as a political opposition that may receive some international support to defend their freedom and usurped rights.

In this context, religious, national and ethnic minorities, especially the Kurds, Assyrians, Druze and others, have suffered from persecution and non-recognition of their political, civil and national rights. This has led to the migration of many of them outside of the country in search of freedom, security and recognition of their national identity. This prompted thousands of Kurds, and Christian Assyrian-Chaldeans in northeastern Syria to head to Iraq, especially seeking refuge in the KRI, to enjoy an atmosphere of freedom and express their identity (Mauvais L., 2022).

4.2. Arrival and reception in Iraq: Figures and social, economic and political reactions

The UNHCR estimated that the number of Syrians residing in Iraq amounted to 250,000 people, all of whom came after the war in Syria in 2011, and about 230,000 of these refugees live in the KRI (see Table No. 1, which shows the number of Syrians entering Iraq after the beginning of the Syrian crisis). As Table No. 1 illustrates, the peak number of Syrians arriving in Iraq was recorded at 248,503 individuals in 2015; of this total, 240,285 were residing in the KRI. Among these, 93,088 were living in camps within the KRI, while the remainder was settled in urban and rural areas outside of these. Approximately 8,000 Syrians were residing in other parts of Iraq, such as Anbar and Baghdad Governorates.

Table 1

Year	Syrian Refugees No. in Iraq	Syrian Refugees No. in KRI	Number inside the camps in KRI	% In the camps	% outside camps
2013	210,612	204,374	79,114	38,71%	61,29%
2014	228,484	220,541	93,800	41,73%	58,27%
2015	248,503	240,285	93,088	38,07%	61,93%
2016	227,971	219,468	87,099	38,87%	61,13%
2017	239,639	231,393	90,816	37,9%	62,10%

(Warda W. et al, 2020, p. 15)

The latest statistics on the number of registered Syrians in the KRI from March 2024 indicate that their number has reached about 258,000. This further indicates that the numbers have not changed much from what was present after the start of the crisis, despite the return of stability in many areas inside Syria. It may also indicate that the return to Syria is met with the migration of many other Syrians outside of the country for work and to improve their economic situation (see Table No. 2 and Chart No. 1):

Table 2

Number of registered Syrian refugees by type of shelter in the Kurdistan Region of Iraq		
Family/Individuals	Year	Value
Family		
Inside the camps	March, 2024	20,290
Outside the camps	March, 2024	53,238
Total:	March, 2024	73,528
Individuals		
Inside the camps	March, 2024	91,389
Outside the camps	March, 2024	166,204
Total:	March, 2024	257,593

(MOJ-KRG, 2024)

Chart 1

(UNHCR, 2024)

Table No. 3 outlines the percentage of Syrians who entered Iraq, categorized by the governorates they originated from. Meanwhile, Table No. 4 pinpoints the precise locations and camps within Iraq where these Syrians were accommodated, along with the number of families and individuals, as well as their corresponding percentages.

Table 3

Governorate of Origin	Percentage of Refugees
Hassakeh	57.81%
Aleppo	24.5%
Damascus	9.51%
Rural Damascus	0.74%
Homs	0.25%
Darah	0.1%
Deir es Zour	2.18%
Other	4.91%
Total	100%

(Warda W. et al, 2018, p. 16)

Table 4

	Camps	Province	Individuals	Ratio	Families	Ratio
1	Domiz 1	Duhok	31,901	35%	8,433	36%
2	Domiz 2	Duhok	8,552	9%	2,072	9%
3	Gawerkosk	Erbil	9,040	10%	2,460	11%
4	Darashakran	Erbil	12,403	13%	2,927	12%
5	Qushtapa	Erbil	7,807	8%	2,124	9%
6	Arabat/ Barika	Sulaymaniya	8,308	9%	2,172	9%
7	Aqrah	Duhok	1,164	1%	284	1%
8	Basirma	Erbil	3,454	4%	805	3%
9	Giwêlan	Duhok	8,187	9%	1,918	9%
10	Al-Obaidi	Anbar	1,519	2%	319	1%
	Total	---	92,235	100%	23,514	100%

(Warda W. et al, 2020, p. 37)

Some refugees have submitted asylum applications to the United Nations (UN) office in Erbil to resettle in a third country. At the same time, another group lives within the region under a residence permit, after obtaining a job or opening up a business (Syria TV, 2021).

We can divide these Syrian refugees into four categories, according to the place of entry and settlement, which are (Hamdo A., 2020):

1. The first category entered through the desert of the Al-Bukamal district and, opposite it, Iraq's Al-Qa'im district, settling in camps far from the cities that only meet a small part of human living requirements. A large segment of these settled in the Anbar Governorate of western Iraq, while another large segment resided in Al-Obaidi Camp and the remainder was hosted by the Arab tribes present there due to their tribal ties, since there is tribal and social overlap between the two countries, especially in the border areas. According to Table 4's the analysis, the percentage of these is estimated to be 2% for individuals and 1% for families.
2. The second group entered Iraq in smaller numbers with a valid visa for religious tourism, settling in the Najaf and Karbala Governorates. In general, this settlement came in areas where Shiite Syrians share close sectarian, ethnic and cultural ties with the host population. Their percentage is estimated to be around 1%.
3. The third category entered via Al-Hasakah and settled in the KRI due to fierce battles that broke out east of the Euphrates River. These people live in better conditions due to the presence of humanitarian organizations and agencies affiliated with the UN that provide a minimum level of humanitarian aid, while the Region's governorates include several camps for Syrian Kurdish and Arab refugees. In Erbil, for example, there are camps at Qushtapa, Darashakran, Giwêlan, Basirma, and Gawerkosk, in Sulaymaniyah there is a camp in the Arabat region, and in Dohuk Governorate, the largest camps for Syrian refugees are spread out in the Domiz and Fayda regions (Sultan A., 2023). Their percentage is estimated at 97% for families and individuals, according to Table No. 3.
4. The fourth category coincided with the rise of racist populist discourse against Syrians in Turkey, especially by a section of extremist Turkish citizens, from which they suffered greatly. This was largely under the pretext that these Syrians compete with Turks in job opportunities, and the large number of refugees had contributed to the rise in food and rental prices inside Turkey. In light of the difficulty of obtaining official residency that helps

them to settle in either Turkey or Lebanon, in addition to the danger and high costs of the migration journey to EU countries, after mid-2023, many Syrian refugees from these two countries flocked to the KRI as a safe haven available to them that guarantees them and their families a decent life (Sultan A., 2023).

Syrians (both Kurds and Christians) residing in the KRI enjoy a special psychological and social status, due to national and religious proximity and the region's distinction in enacting laws to protect religious and ethnic minorities, especially Law No. 5 of 2011, which grants religious and ethnic components broad protection of their rights, at a time when such a law is not even available under Iraq's federal government. Obtaining an entry visa to the Region's territory is considered one of the easiest visas, compared to those of other countries and even that of the Baghdad Government, as it only requires some simple legal procedures. For their part, the Regional authorities encouraged the migration of Syrian Kurds to the KRI, in order to increase the population density and general Kurdish presence (Sultan A., 2023). Recently, however, and specifically in April 2024, the leadership of the Region's authorities stopped granting visas and did not allow entry visas to be given to Syrians, even families, except for those who had interview appointments at foreign embassies and consulates within the Region (Syria Direct, 2024). As for Syrians whose residency has expired, they must leave the region before the end of the legal period of residency and it is not possible to renew it, according to the decision of the KRI's Interior Ministry. This policy came due to pressure from the federal government on the Kurdistan Regional Government (KRG) to apply its procedures, instructions and laws to all of Iraq, especially labor laws and visa procedures, as well as the KRG's desire for this policy due to Syrian competition with Iraqi Kurds in the labor market, as well as the high prices of food and the cost of housing.¹

According to statistics issued by the World Food Programme and the UNHCR, Syrian refugees living in KRI camps generally face alarming levels of food. These statistics confirm that about 86% of these refugees who live in Iraqi camps, estimated at 78,000 people, suffer from food insecurity, or are at risk of it, due to successive social and economic shocks, besides restrictions on entry to and exit from the camps (UN, 2022), in addition to harsh working conditions and low wages (Syria TV, 2023). Families' reliance on informal and unstable jobs, in exchange for low cash wages in the informal economy, is a major cause and contributor to the exacerbation of food insecurity. Vulnerable families are forced to resort to negative coping strategies, such as buying food on credit, reducing expenditures on basic foods, selling their belongings, engaging in child labor and being forced to drop out of school, because job opportunities dry up (Al-Tatoos S., 2022). These conditions pressure many to return, especially those whose original places of residence in Syria are not in areas of danger or armed conflicts.

The segment of Syrian residents who came to Iraq without a passport or identification papers are placed in special refugee camps. On the other hand, those who entered Iraq officially, after obtaining a visa, undergo various other procedures to gain access by submitting an entry visa application through tourism and travel offices in their home country, provided that those offices have a branch in Iraq. The authorities responsible for issuing visas or residence permits in Iraq are the Iraqi MOI and the KRI's Interior Ministry, which is responsible for the entry of Syrians

¹ HHRO roundtable workshop with stakeholders and expert persons (SEP), held in Baghdad on April 6, 2024.

through licensed companies affiliated with the state, of which are about 50, and each of these is allowed to issue about 400 visas and residence permits. The tourist visa fee ranges from 100 to 200 US dollars, with clear conditions including a passport valid for more than 6 months, noting that Iraq was the first to recognize the new Syrian passport after many Arab and foreign countries refused to deal with it (Sultan A., 2023).² The entry visa is issued within a few days of applying for it, and it is valid for one month and can be renewed every month for a specific fee. There are two types of visas: tourist and work visas. Most Syrians, however, obtain a tourist visa because it is easier, and it is then converted into a work permit through a lawyer, after which the applicant obtains an annual residency that can be renewed for a fee of \$500-600. This is a large amount, posing a dilemma for some families that include many members. Moreover, if anyone violates residency conditions, they are fined \$12 for each day and, in the event of non-payment, they are deported from the Region and a note is placed prohibiting their re-entry for five years (Syr-SNH-Micro-F).

As long as Iraq does not have a comprehensive refugee law and Syrians in Iraq are not considered refugees, they are treated with different policies. Sometimes, they are considered guests and, at other times, foreign residency laws are applied to them, just like any other foreigner in Iraq. Residency Law No. 76 of 2017, which regulates the entry of expatriates into the country as well as the organization of their work and residence, applies to them just like other foreigners (MOJ, 2017). Syrians in Iraq are subject to the country's laws if they commit any offense or crime that is legally punishable. In most cases, major offenses or crimes are rarely committed, except for the issue of residence period expiration and the recent difficulties in renewing it, as a result of imposing fines on violators and many Syrians' inability to pay them (Syria TV, 2023). These government measures have impacted Syrians' legal situation and have put strong pressure on their stay in Iraq, forcing them to consider either returning to Syria or migrating to other countries.

4.3. The social, economic and political conditions and events that led to the development of governance of return migration from Iraq to Syria

The influx of Syrian refugees into Iraq has had both positive and negative consequences for both Iraqis and Syrians. The exhaustion of infrastructure and services, and the pressure on the housing, labor and education sectors, which Iraq already suffers from, are among the negative effects resulting from the influx of a large number of Syrians into and residing in Iraq. Consequently, their number has increased the deterioration and weakness in these sectors. In addition, the difficulty of absorbing these large numbers of Syrians poses a major challenge to the Iraqi Government and its ability to provide them the necessary support, leading to social, psychological and economic changes that negatively affect both Iraqi society and Syrian residents alike.

Perhaps the only positive aspect of the issue of Syrian immigration to Iraq is the increase in the size of the workforce, including a fair number of experienced people and technicians, which has had a positive impact on driving the economy and achieving development. All of this is

² The new passport was issued by the Bashar al-Assad Government after the internal unrest that hit the country, both for security reasons as well as to impede the emigration of wanted individuals. This constituted an obstacle for a large number of Syrians wishing to travel outside the country, but not for those heading to Iraq.

reflected negatively for the parent country (Syria), which will suffer from a weakness in the workforce and other competencies, as well as a major economic recession, in return for achieving some economic gains through the financial transfers made by Syrians working in Iraq to their relatives and families back home. Nevertheless, the latter constitutes an important economic resource in hard currency that may help Syrians drive their economy in one way or another.

Given that the rest of Iraq's governorates enjoy better employment opportunities and conditions, as well as higher wages than those in the KRI, this has led to the illegal movement of many Syrians from there to the rest of the country through smuggling and infiltration. Due to the growing number of Syrians staying beyond their permitted time, detention centers are at capacity, and some of these individuals have engaged in prohibited activities such as begging. Recent complications have arisen for Syrians coming to Iraq or residing there, due to competition for job opportunities and the inability of Iraqis to obtain a job after the issuance of new instructions by the KRI's Interior Ministry determining the percentages of foreign workers in non-governmental service sectors such as hotels, restaurants, factories, the construction sector, and others. In this context, the Iraqi federal security authorities have arrested hundreds of Syrians who had crossed the border seeking humanitarian asylum, to ensure the integrity of their positions and their non-affiliation with terrorist organizations or groups banned in Iraq. They were detained at various prisons between Mosul and Baghdad, and some of them were charged with illegally crossing the border, while others were placed under investigation (Al-Jazeera, 2023). The Iraqi authorities claim that the detention is to verify their identity and their non-affiliation with extremist or banned groups. If their innocence is proven, they are given a choice between being returned to their country or sent to a third country. As for those proven to be involved in acts that affect national security, they will be dealt with legally under the applicable Iraqi laws. These harsh measures taken by the federal government have negatively affected the security and stability of Syrians residing in Iraq, and have tightened the noose around them. They are also forcing them to think about finding other alternatives that provide them with reassurance and an easy life. These Iraqi measures appear to be aimed at introducing economic and security reforms in order to govern migration and return, as well as establishing policies for political and security stability in Iraq.

In this context, the Iraqi authorities launched a large-scale campaign in early May 2024 to pursue foreigners violating the residency law in Baghdad. This resulted in the arrest of 555 residency conditions violators of various nationalities, including dozens of Syrians, with those who have a visa for the KRI deported there. An informed source, who requested to remain anonymous, was present during the arrest operation and indicated to us that the force carrying out the duty arrested only Syrian men. They were returned to the KRI and those who had families there were received by Regional authorities without any accountability, as long as they had residency there. On the other hand, Syrians who neither had families nor KRI residency were forcibly deported to Syria. Due to the security blackout, it is not possible to know the exact numbers of those forcibly returned or even the nature of these returns. North Press also quoted Rashid Ali Jan as saying that 13 young Syrians were forcibly deported from Baghdad International Airport to Damascus International Airport, and four of them were arrested and taken to Syrian Government security centers upon their arrival (Syria TV, 2023).

Due to the Iraqi measures taken against Syrians, a group of Syrian activists and humanitarian organizations organized a protest in front of the UN representation in Erbil and submitted a protest memorandum to them demanding the release of more than 400 Syrians detained by the Iraqi government, some of whom, as previously mentioned, are in Mosul prison and others in Baghdad prisons (Al-Jazeera, 2023). After that, the head of the Jani Roj Charity organization, Mr. Rashid Ali Jan, held a press conference calling on the Iraqi government, the KRG, and the UN to reform the process of releasing detainees because they are refugees and their detention contradicts the principles of the Iraqi constitution, since their entry into Iraq is first and foremost a humanitarian matter. He also pointed out that the Iraqi authorities' handing over of some Syrians to the Syrian Government is an illegal step according to the principles of international law and unconstitutional according to the Iraqi constitution. Moreover, there are no clear bilateral agreements granting the authority to repatriate refugees. He further explained that the detainees are Syrian Arabs and Kurds, and that the only reason for their arrest was their illegal and unofficial entry into Iraq as refugees (Syria TV, 2023).

5. Characteristics of the governance of return migration from Iraq to Syria

5.1. Statistics, numbers and volume of return

Unfortunately, there is no accurate official information or complete documented statistics on the number of Syrians returning home from Iraq. The official Iraqi side is almost uncooperative in revealing much of this information. Our research team tried to communicate directly or indirectly with stakeholders specialized in this field, such as the MOMD, the MOI, the MOFA, the Ministry of Planning (MOP), and some other official bodies, but we did not observe any transparency on this subject, except for a small number of them and in a limited manner. Therefore, we relied on some reliable media sources, in addition to the interviews we conducted with many Syrians who have information on this subject. As for the official Syrian side, it is perhaps more secretive, confidential and reserved in providing any information related to Syrians, in addition to the difficulty for our researchers to directly contact any interested party on that side, as this would cause them a major problem that could expose them to legal accountability or even reach the level of administrative punishment. This is because the Assad Government deals with such issues as a matter of national security. The information related to it is therefore confidential and, if any person provides any unauthorized information or statement, this is considered treason and falls within the framework of communicating with foreign parties, which is considered a crime punishable by Syrian law, putting their life at risk. This is what some Syrians residing in Iraq confirmed during our interview with them (Syr-ASA-Micro-M).

The actuality of Syrians' return is mostly voluntary or forced. Sometimes, these two types of return intersect, as most Syrian returnees returned naturally, but in reality, this was a forced return due to the lack of options available to Syrian residents wishing to stay in Iraq, so it is more like a forced return in a voluntary guise. This accurate description of the Syrian return migration situation is due to several main factors, including activating the implementation of labor laws in Iraqi Kurdistan. Labor Law No. 71 of 1987, which is still in effect in the Region and Instruction No. 2 of 2007, regarding foreign labor in the Region, both emphasize the necessity of granting Iraqi private sector workers the largest share of the labor market. Thus, large numbers of Syrian private sector workers in Iraqi Kurdistan will be laid off.

As for Syrians working outside the Region, the federal government has tightened the application of the current Iraqi Labor Law No. 37 of 2015, noting that this law has not yet been applied in the KRI, as well as the Retirement and Social Security Law No. 18 of 2023. This is also likely to reflect the same results and make large numbers of Syrians unemployed because it emphasizes observing the conditions for foreigners to work in Iraq, including work permits and registration in social security records. These are difficult and exhausting requirements, especially after their work in the rest of Iraq's governorates brought them a good profit, through which they could meet their daily needs and send other amounts to their families in Syria. Syrians working in Iraq obtain good financial revenues that constitute a good source of income for them and their families back home. On the other hand, these financial transfers revive their country's deteriorating economy, and in fact, they do not see any point in returning there, even if its situation stabilizes, as long as they can earn interest and money from staying in Iraq. After a Syrian

loses their opportunity to work, they will certainly be forced to return or engage in illegal and unlawful work, immigrate to EU or other countries through smuggling and illegal means, or work secretly for very low wages. If they are arrested by the authorities, they will be forcibly deported. In other words, the great economic pressure that Syrians are exposed to in Iraq forces some of them to choose to return to Syria (Syr-MNA-Micro-M). On the surface, this is a voluntary return, but its essence and reality is a forced one.

In the same context, UN-accredited journalist Dina Abi Saab says that: “the return of any refugee in the world is not supposed to be forced, and a refugee must remain a refugee as long as their country is suffering from war and is classified as a country at war.” As long as the end of the war in Syria has not been declared, and the Syrians outside the country’s borders are present as forced refugees, their return there may mean their arrest, or their only option would be to leave their country and live in another country (Redress, 2016). The procedures of forced deportation of Syrians, and their return to conflict zones and dangerous areas, add new victims to the forced return policies.

In general, the economic sanctions imposed by the United States on Syria, including the Caesar Act, have greatly contributed to delaying the return of millions of Syrians to their country. This is one of the main obstacles of their return, in addition to the lack of clear official guidelines from Syrian authorities, through which returning Syrians can find specific methods that guarantee them transparent access to information about whether they are wanted by a certain party, how to resolve this problem, or even the possibility of obtaining their official papers, such as a national ID or passport, which many Syrians lost during their migration journey (for those living within the authority of the official government and its supporting forces). As for those living outside this area, such as those controlled by the Syrian Democratic Forces (SDF) in northeastern Syria, and Idlib, which is controlled by Hay’at Tahrir al-Sham (HTS) and other armed factions, they face further difficulty in obtaining their official identification papers because the forces holding the territory there do not recognize Damascus’ authority, and have their own records and identification papers, such as identity cards, driver’s licenses, and title deeds for example, which are regulated and issued by the authorities occupying the land. This constitutes a dangerous intersection and chaos for any person seeking to move within Syria (OHCHR, 2024).

Fear and lack of suitable options can push Syrian refugees to take dangerous paths. In many cases, these are exacerbated by family ties and the desire of Syrian families to keep their children away from conflict areas and the dangers of war, as well as the poor and difficult economic conditions in the areas of Iraq where they are located. These are strong incentives for them, especially young people, to take such dangerous paths and decisions, such as being used by smugglers and human traffickers or returning to the dangerous conflict areas from which they fled in Syria. In some cases, failure to obtain a durable solution may amount to a form of cruel or inhumane treatment. If this is a reason for voluntary return, it can at the same time be described as a forced return in the guise of a voluntary one, and it may also actually constitute a form of forced return. It is therefore difficult to separate the basic obligation not to return forcibly from others imposed on states according to the Refugee Convention. Iraq is still bound by the principle of non-refoulement under international law, and Syria is not a safe country for many people (Redress, 2016, p. 13).

Some Syrians However, reported in statements to media agencies that about 500 Syrians have been forcibly deported from Iraq to Syria for security reasons, which in turn could expose them in security problems (Syria TV, 2023). After being interviewed, some Syrians revealed that their friends who had returned home had informed them that some of the returnees had disappeared and that contact with them inside the country had been cut off. Some of them had been arrested because they were wanted for military service or because they were indicated to be opponents of the Syrian regime. Some of them even had no problem with Syrian government authorities and their names were not in the lists of those wanted or of the regime's opponents, but they also faced the same problem (OHCHR, 2024).

5.2. The main actors in the return of Syrians to their country

In this section, we can identify two levels of actors who control the file of the reverse of Syrian immigration to Iraq. The first and most important level is at that of actors in Iraq, the country of residence, and these are divided into two categories. The first is related to the federal government, which is responsible for designing and implementing policies for such displacement cases. This is represented by MOFA through its embassies abroad and human rights office, focusing on Iraqi citizens residing abroad, MOI through the residence department responsible for granting entry visas to foreigners, and the Permanent Committee for Refugee Affairs, which is responsible for the file of refugees in Iraq. The latter is primarily responsible for registering arrivals to Iraq, both at the federal government level and that of the KRI, especially after its tasks were expanded in 2016, according to a memorandum of understanding between it and the KRG, as well as coordinating and cooperating with the UNHCR (Warda W. et al, 2020, p. 14). This committee is also responsible for coordination between the federal government and the KRG.

On the other hand, the Joint Crisis Coordination Center (JCC)³ is responsible for coordination and cooperation between KRG institutions, and international and local organizations operating in the KRI, in providing humanitarian services to refugees, as well as coordinating with federal government institutions concerned with humanitarian and refugee services. The aforementioned Permanent Committee for Refugee Affairs also issues decisions and formulates and implements policies regarding the admission or deportation of refugees. The MOI, at both the federal and KRG levels, is responsible for the forcible deportation of those who violate residency conditions or are convicted of crimes under Iraqi law. As for voluntary return, the Iraqi MOMD (at the federal government level) and the KRG cooperate and coordinate through the JCC. The scope of work and procedures for dealing with Syrians is within the powers and instructions of the MOI, in addition to the Iraqi National Intelligence Service (INIS) and the Iraqi National Security Service (INSS). These are responsible for implementing policies related to Syrians, from arrival to reception to enter into Iraqi territory, whether inside camps or freely, as well as coordinating the relationship between the federal government and the KRG through the latter's representative office within the General Secretariat of the federal government's Council of Ministers.

The other section is linked to the KRG, represented by the MOI, the Ministry of Labor and Social Affairs (MOLSA), the Internal Security Agency (Asayish). There is also collaboration with

³ An office established in 2014 that carries out coordination tasks between different institutions in the Kurdistan Region of Iraq, in terms of providing services, humanitarian assistance and protection to refugees, as well as coordinating with federal government institutions in this regard.

the JCC, which organizes work with foreigners and international organizations concerned with migration and asylum, and coordinates with all institutions and ministries in the KRI and the federal government regarding the humanitarian aspect (JCC, 2014). In general, the KRG worked largely independently of the federal government, as it has given a space of freedom and better reception conditions for Syrians than their peers residing in the rest of Iraq's governorates.

The second category is the non-governmental side of the Civil Society Organizations (CSOs) and NGOs, whose job is to coordinate with actors inside Iraq, to overcome the obstacles and difficulties that Syrians may face there, by holding meetings, submitting reports and case studies or a position assessment, whether to the federal government, KRG, or UN.

The second level is that of actors in the home country, Syria, namely the Syrian Interior Ministry, which is responsible for granting security clearances for travel in coordination and cooperation with the Syrian MOFA through its embassy in Iraq, the Syrian Intelligence Service, and Syrian security services, which consist of many branches. Syrians cannot officially travel to any country without security clearance, even if they have obtained a visa. For those who enter Iraq, however, through the crossings linked to the KRI, such as those at Simalka and Fayshkhabur, this process takes place after obtaining the necessary approvals by the SDF, in coordination and cooperation with Iraqi authorities in the KRI. Syrians coming to Iraq must submit an application to the SDF security authorities, and after approval, coordination is made with Iraqi authorities in the KRI to approve entry into Iraqi territory, after obtaining a guarantee from an Iraqi citizen. Syrians are often in contact with Iraqi companies, businessmen, or relatives to make this personal guarantee.

5.3. Policies

Regarding the protection of refugees and the return process, Iraq relies primarily on international organizations and the assistance they provide, especially the UNHCR, and in coordination and cooperation with the International Organization for Migration (IOM), specifically on the issue of voluntary return. Statistics on voluntary return are often controlled by international organizations more than the government side, because most Syrians in Iraq are registered with the UNHCR as asylum seekers. Additionally, the lack of coordination between Iraqi institutions, especially the MOI and the MOMD, negatively affects finding accurate data for returnees. Sometimes, Syrians return voluntarily without informing the MOMD and policies regarding migration in Iraq are quite diverse and varied. On the one hand, Iraq considers Syrians in Iraq to be guests while, on the other hand, it treats them as foreigners – according to the residency law for foreigners – in terms of length of stay, renewal of residency, fines, etc.

The absence of appropriate solutions to address the refugee or Syrian resident situation in Iraq, and reliance on humanitarian aid provided by civil society organizations in the long term, will further exacerbate the tragic situation of refugees, whether in camps or elsewhere. This may force some of them to resort to illegal means to obtain money and expose another group of them to physical abuse, torture, rape, increased child labor and the spread of begging cases (Redress, 2016).

In this context, we have noticed increasing cooperation between the KRG and the federal government on the issue of governance of return migration, as coordination between the two sides begun in 2016 through the Standing Committee for Refugee Affairs, affiliated with the MOI and headed by the federal government's Deputy Interior Minister, has been increasing and is becoming more organized. The central computer systems of border crossings between the KRI and Federal Government, responsible for checking the names of individuals wanted by the Iraqi judiciary or Interpol, were linked. This happened after the KRG had been operating independently from the Federal Government. Additionally, the JCC includes a large number of administrative and official figures from the KRI, to address the obstacles and difficulties facing Syrians residing in Iraq and other displaced persons and refugees, as well as those problems that stand in the way of governance of return migration (HRW, 2024). It is further responsible for coordinating work and activities, and drawing up joint policies, besides reaching joint decisions and results that are free from sympathy.

As for the Iraqi side, despite having a special law on political asylum, it is working on issuing a more comprehensive immigration law for dealing with all forms of return. The Iraqi Government has also developed a plan to reduce illegal immigration called the Comprehensive National Plan to Reduce Illegal Immigration, according to a letter from the General Secretariat of the Council of Ministers – Department of Cabinet Affairs and Committees No. (Sh.Z.L/10/1/Circulars/1718, dated 11/1/2023). This includes the formation of a committee to prepare a comprehensive national plan to reduce illegal immigration, in cooperation and coordination with the relevant authorities, headed by the MOMD, and with the membership of representatives from relevant ministries. Due to the increase in the number of illegal immigrants, this plan focused on developing activities that limit this phenomenon and finding appropriate

solutions for it, by distributing responsibilities to the implementing agencies within a specific time frame.⁴

Iraq is also cooperating with the EU to provide assistance and rehabilitate its institutions and capacities, in order to deal with returnees and the governance of return migration. Recently, at the end of 2023, Iraq developed a national referral program with the assistance of the EU and a number of individual European governments, to take care of the status of returnees (Iraqi News Agency, 2022), as well as cooperation and coordination with relevant international organizations such as the UNHCR and IOM, and opening the way for cooperation with relevant civil society organizations in providing services to returnees and refugees (3MOHM-Meso-M).

The HHRO's experience as part of the Returning Working Group (RWG) has produced several important results that have been analyzed by researchers and linked to the issue of return migration governance.⁵ As such, it held a specialized workshop in the form of a roundtable regarding the GAP's project to discuss the policies of the return of migrants, readmission and integration, with stakeholders including some officials and researchers, in April 2024. The attendees included representatives of the General Secretariat of the Council of Ministers, the MOP, the IOM, the MOLSA, and international organizations such as the International Center for Migration Policy Development (ICMPD) and European Technology and Training Centre (ETTC).

Iraq's constitution firmly upholds the principle of non-refoulement, meaning that no one should be forcibly returned to a place where they face danger, and this is also backed by the international human rights agreements that Iraq has signed. Further demonstrating its commitment, Iraq was a founding member of the Global Compact for Migration in 2018, which champions safe, orderly, and regular returns.⁶ So, any forced return of Syrians to Syria would be a direct violation of both Iraq's own constitution and its international commitments or obligations. Unfortunately, however, there have been reports of Iraq forcibly returning some Syrians after they were arrested for entering the country irregularly. These actions clearly contradict with Iraq's international obligations and Article 21 paragraph 2 of the Iraqi Constitution.⁷

The stakeholder expert persons (SEP) roundtable discussion revealed several obstacles and challenges that making the return of Syrians to Syria difficult, that include:

- 1- The policies adopted in Iraq so far do not cover the needs of returnees, especially what was indicated by those who were interviewed. These include basic requirements represented by travel costs for the return, besides other sums that may help them for a limited period during their return to their country, and to secure living requirements until they obtain work, in addition to the special secondary requirements that must regulate the legal status of Syrians residing in Iraq as refugees and not guests.

⁴ *Comprehensive National Plan to Reduce Illegal Immigration*, prepared by: The Supreme Committee to Reduce Illegal Immigration, August 2023.

⁵ RWG is a group of international and national Iraqi civil society organizations working to support the return of displaced refugees to their areas of origin. It holds periodic meetings and issues reports on the levels and developments of the situation in Iraq. It is primarily concerned with the displaced and internally displaced.

⁶ See: *The Global Compact for Migration*, 2018.

⁷ *Iraqi Constitution*, 2005.

- 2- The legal and procedural environment in the migration process, or the governance of return migration, does not meet the ambition and desired goal, because it is still deficient and does not conform to the international legal environment, in light of mechanisms adopted by the UN and IOM. This is because Iraqi legislation still suffers from stagnation in some of its paragraphs, due to the novelty of the situation and the lack of previous experience in the field of receiving refugees, compared to international legislation. For instance, the 1951 *UN Convention relating to the Status of Refugees* prohibits the principle of expulsion or forced return of persons considered refugees, except in some cases associated with the issue of national security or public order, as in Articles 32 and 33 of that Convention (Redress, 2016, p. 13; UNHCR, 2009). This Convention also prohibits the principle of torture, ill-treatment or persecution in Article 1. Accordingly, every country in which a person is subject to its jurisdiction must fulfill its obligations under the *UN Convention against Torture*, including countries of origin, transit countries and countries of destination.⁸
- 3- Some Iraqi government institutions, such as the MOMD, the Permanent Committee for Refugee Affairs and the National Security Advisory, have succeeded in enhancing their experience by following appropriate mechanisms to improve the situation of returnees. These institutions' efforts have been engaged with international ones, such as those of the EU, the UNHCR and the IOM, to develop and improve the situation of Syrian residents, as well as to cooperate in finding appropriate solutions to overcome the difficulties they face, whether during their presence in Iraq or upon their return to Syria. This is by distributing supplies like food items and medication, as well as fuel and hygiene products, along with additional logistical support such as blankets and essential electrical devices to those in need, during emergencies. Other institutions, however, are still dealing with this matter with reservations, such as the security services that avoid providing us with information or declaring it under the pretext of maintaining national security.
- 4- There is a weakness in coordination between the parties concerned with the rights of returnees, especially between security institutions and civil institutions, and a lack of well-organized frameworks for joint work between them to facilitate the governance of the return migration process, as well as transparency in the exchange of information between these parties.
- 5- There is a deficiency in most civil society organizations in Iraq, in understanding the civil responsibilities they have, to care for the rights of returnees, in addition to the great deficiency in coordination and follow-up mechanisms. In this context, there is no information yet about civil organizations that understand the importance of working with the government or other civil organizations to ensure services that should be provided to returnees.
- 6- Despite the existence of decisions and work regulations to support the concept of return, there are government decisions that encourage migration, including poor job opportunities. If we take the description that 80% of migrants are due to obtaining the opportunity of a decent life abroad, and that most of these are from the youth sector, the

⁸ See: Article 3 of the *UN Convention against Torture* and Article 7 of the *International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights* of 1966.

- lack of job opportunities thus leads, to a large extent, to refugees returning to their country or considering another place of refuge.
- 7- There is a routine bureaucracy within official institutions in dealing with procedures that must be followed to guarantee the rights of returnees, which consumes a lot of time, effort and money for Syrians.
 - 8- The procedures for ensuring return have not risen to a level that allows returnees to feel reassured about their future after their return, as the drivers of Syrian migration are still in place, while those of return are weak. Syrians do not have motives or incentives that would make them think about returning and settling in Syria, due to the weak economic and social situations resulting from the fragmentation and demographic change in many areas of the country (e.g., the absence of friends, neighbors, or relatives), which pushes Syrians to head to safe havens such as Europe.
 - 9- There are reservations among several government institutions regarding providing explanatory data, numbers, and information about returnees, under pretexts that are not consistent with human rights, which has negatively affected the formation of accurate field convictions regarding such a return.
 - 10- Family divisions occur among returnees, most of which are related to forced return, or for social reasons such as marriage, divorce, and others.

5.4. Practices

At the beginning of the Syrian displacement crisis in 2011, there was no joint coordination between the KRI's institutions and those of the federal government. The KRG exercised political and administrative independence from Baghdad to a large extent, and established laws and instructions that were consistent with its own interests. The issue of Syrian displacement was almost a surprise, not only to the Region but also to Baghdad, since the situation in Iraq since the 1980s was almost unqualified environmentally to accept refugees. This is because it was a repellent rather than attractive environment, due to the state of continuous wars and the poor economic situation that Iraq was living through at that period. Moreover, after 2003, and the spread and escalation of violence during the internal war between 2006 and 2008, then the control of ISIS in 2014 over a third of Iraq, the experience of receiving refugees in the country, especially Syrians, was not studied or planned, and most likely came in the form of mass influxes, however, Iraq gradually observed the crisis.

In the same context, the Iraqi Supreme Judicial Council and highest judicial authority banned the deportation of any Syrian resident in Iraq in August 2023. On March 18, 2024, however, Iraqi authorities represented by the MOI launched a campaign targeting foreigners who had violated residency laws, leading to the detention and deportation of many Syrians after their homes or workplaces were raided. In Erbil, the KRG suspended the issuance of visas to Syrians on April 3, 2024, at the federal government's request, and in line with the government's plan to regulate foreign labor that is negatively impacting the labor market and employment opportunities for Iraqi workers (HRW, 2024).

6. Governance of the driving forces of return migration from Iraq to Syria

6.1. Interests in the governance of return migration

A. At the local level:

Two levels of interest are considered influences that constitute a constraint or incentive for staying or returning. At the local level, which is represented by Iraq, the host country, and in the field of support for staying, there is the influence of some parties on that file, especially in the KRI. Some of these parties (the ruling parties) have used Syrians as tools for political agendas to compete internally, by pushing and encouraging Syrian Kurds and Christians to stay and settle in the KRI in order to resettle them, and there are even allegations that some of them have obtained Iraqi citizenship, which the party benefits from to expand its popular base and allow its increased representation in the Iraqi or Regional parliaments (Syr-MNA-Micro-M). In the same context, the Region's encouragement for Syrians to stay is a result of the success of a large number of them in the modern tourism industry in Kurdistan, in addition to their transfer of much of their expertise in the fields of manufacturing food and other materials, and this has been transferred to the rest of Iraq's Governorates. Despite the integration of many experienced and skilled Syrians working within the authority of the federal government, however, they continued to suffer from the difficulty of renewing residence permits due to Iraq's reliance on the Residency Law for Foreigners of 2017 and the absence of a comprehensive refugee law, except for a single one on political asylum, No. 51 of 1971. The federal government approach, therefore, is to regulate the Syrian presence in Iraq, but the KRG wants to integrate Syrians of Kurdish origin into Kurdish society due to considerations of internal competition between Baghdad and Erbil.

As for the policies of supporting the return migration of Syrians, several problems and obstacles push them to return to Syria – not only for Syrian Arabs but even for Syrian Kurds, who have begun to suffer from the problem of integration and the nature of education in the Region. The problem for Syrian children who speak the Kurmanji dialect of Kurdish (one of the dialects spoken by Kurds in Syria and Turkey, and differing from the Sorani dialect spoken or written in the educational curricula at Erbil and Sulaymaniyah) has made it difficult for them to integrate and learn in Erbil, where people speak the Sorani dialect. In addition, the issuance of new controls and restrictions forces them to return or pay thousands of dollars in fines for violating residency requirements (Syr-SMH-Micro-F).

B. On the external level:

On the external level related to the country of origin (Syria), the factors that attract and encourage return migration are summarized by the improved security situation in many of the country's governorates and regions, as well as the issuance of some statements and decisions that encourage the return of Syrians. These include the amnesty decision issued for those who had violated mandatory conscription or evaded military service, on the condition that the citizen is not wanted for political reasons or affiliated with armed groups, and the decision to pay a cash conscription

allowance for an expatriate in the amount of \$8,000 after he has spent at least 5 years outside Syria. This forces the expatriate Syrian to face the choice of either securing this large sum of money during these five years, or considering emigration to Europe as a better option (Syr-MNA-Micro-M). These measures and policies in themselves are a positive step to encourage return, but in reality, they are dedicated to political agendas through which the Syrian regime aimed to:

- Lure Syrian youth living abroad to return and use them as tools to mobilize its military capabilities, as well as harness their skills and expertise to rebuild the infrastructure of the military machine and other regime institutions, or in the fields of reconstruction and the economy, which has largely deteriorated.
- Put political pressure on neighboring countries hosting Syrian refugees that suffer from deteriorating economic conditions, such as Iraq, Lebanon and Turkey, and promote the existence of job opportunities available in Syria as part of reconstruction programs, which may be unrealistic in light of the current circumstances in the country.
- Send conflicting media messages about the security and economic situation in Syria, which increases confusion among Syrian refugees in neighboring countries (Syr-WKS-Micro-M).

On the other hand, these measures and policies followed by the Syrian regime reflect on the governance of return migration in Iraq, which may push decision-makers there to push Syrians residing in the country to return, as long as the regime had sent positive messages toward that. At the same time, Syrians residing in Iraq remain afraid to return due to the fragile security situation, or the fact that areas in Syria are not yet safe, as well as the deteriorating economic situation in the country, which is a major obstacle to return migration. This includes the low value of the Syrian Pound and some expensive costs paid by Syrian citizens to avoid legal accountability (Syr-SMH-Micro-F).

It can therefore be stated that the crisis in Syria has affected the interests of Iraq, as well as its economic and security dimensions. The number of Syrians stranded within Iraq has therefore enriched the country with more man power, expertise and skills but has also posed a demographic, social and economic challenge. Some of them have been involved in currency smuggling, drug trafficking, human trafficking, organ trafficking, etc. (Syr-MNA-Micro-M).

6.2. Return migration management capabilities

Regarding the capacities of the relevant stakeholders in Syria, despite the existence of constitutional and legal guarantees to protect return migration, the infrastructure and human resources are not qualified to implement this due to the Syrian regime's security nature and its rigid attitudes that interfere with the rights and freedoms guaranteed by international conventions and the Syrian constitution.

Whatever the legal frameworks and tools that help Syrian residents to return to their country are, this matter is primarily linked to the security map in Syria, the level of confidence in the country's security situation, besides the economic and political situation. The legitimacy and possibility of return, whether voluntary or forced, therefore, depends on these elements, because the guarantees of return are not limited to the constitutional, legal and political guarantees of either country only, but rather extend to the economic situation, the judiciary, justice, as well as the field of human rights and freedoms. The 2012 Syrian Constitution protects many basic rights

in its provisions. Article 38 stipulates that citizens shall not be prevented from returning, and gives them the right to move to any place within the country or leave it, unless prohibited by a judicial decision from the court. Violence, conflict and violations continue in an organized manner, despite the noticeable decrease in military operations inside Syria, violating the rules of international humanitarian and human rights law. The earthquakes that struck the country's northwestern in February 2023 also increased the humanitarian disaster for Syrians, especially displaced persons living in camps or temporary housing, as statistics indicate that nearly 6,000 people were killed as a result (OHCHR, 2024).

In the context of the return issue, the UN and international organizations and NGO's are constantly warning governments and NGOs of the repercussions of the forced return of refugees to Syria. They have called for a halt to the illegal deportation of refugees for fear that they will be tortured or killed by the Assad regime upon their return, especially since the necessary conditions for a safe and peaceful return have not yet been met. The UN takes into consideration many issues regarding the return of refugees, the most important of which is the risk to life, depending on their political orientations regarding the Syrian issue, and that no form of pressure is exerted on them. It is also trying to secure the minimum standard of living for refugees registered with it, such as financial assistance, infrastructure, water and electricity services. The increasing level of poverty in the host countries contributes to accelerating these demands to return refugees to their home countries, in addition to the growth of hate speech against Syrians in the KRI and other areas of Iraq. Due to competition for access to work and the economic pressures experienced by host countries, the KRI has completely banned the entry of Syrians (Kassos S., 2023).

6.3. The role of the European Union as a driving force for managing return migration from Iraq to Syria

The EU did not have a major role in developing programs or plans to help Iraq return Syrians to Syria, despite the fact that it has coordination and agreements with countries hosting them, including Iraq, to re-admit refugees and organize mechanisms to return them to their countries of origin in a safe and orderly manner. This is due to the political reality, as a result of the political convergence between decision-makers and policies in Baghdad with the policies of the authorities in Syria, as well as work to align with its approach on many issues, including the Syrian file. There was even cooperation between Iraq and the EU in resettlement programs for Syrians, whether to European countries such as Sweden, or others or to countries outside Europe such as America and Australia (MH-Meso-M).

However, the EU has not stopped performing its other tasks in supporting returning Syrians financially and logistically, through funding resettlement programs that aim to help refugees return to their homes and rebuild their lives. These programs include supporting livelihoods and providing small loans to establish small businesses. The EU has also worked to support the reconstruction of basic infrastructure in Syria such as schools, roads and hospitals, as well as supporting the private sector through training and skills development programs, in order to access new job opportunities and revitalize the Syrian economy (European Commission, 2024).

The EU has not stopped implementing awareness programs for Syrian refugees and providing them with sufficient information about the return process and life in Syria. At the same

time, it provides means of protection by assessing the risks to which returning refugees may be exposed, as well as psychosocial rehabilitation programs for returning refugees, to help them adapt to new conditions and overcome psychological trauma. In addition, there is a lot of legal assistance that the EU offers to the returned refugees, such as the restoration of documents and the registration of new born children (Reliefweb, 2020).

Simultaneously, the EU initiated joint measures with partner countries on Syria's rehabilitation and growth and held meetings of donor and host countries, as well as international organizations. These were to discuss issues related to Syrian refugees, with an emphasis on making efforts toward fostering peace and supporting political solutions to the crisis in Syria, monitoring the human rights situation, and pressing the Syrian Government under the Assad regime to address humanitarian needs (Reliefweb, 2020).

On the EU front, the governments of eight EU member states said in a joint statement that the situation in Syria must be assessed to allow the voluntary return of Syrian refugees to their homeland. Officials from Austria, the Czech Republic, Cyprus, Denmark, Greece, Italy, Malta and Poland said in the declaration that they had agreed to a reassessment that would lead to "more effective ways of dealing" with Syrian refugees trying to reach EU countries. The eight countries, who held talks at a summit in the Cypriot capital Nicosia, said the situation in Syria had improved significantly, although full political stability had not been achieved.

The countries stressed that the EU must increase its support to Lebanon "to mitigate the risks of greater influxes of Syrian refugees from Lebanon to the EU." They also indicated that, despite their full backing for the need to support Syrian refugees, in line with international law, they believe that their talks should lead to a broader discussion within the EU bloc about granting migrants international protection. They also explained that "decisions regarding who has the right to cross the borders of an EU member state should be taken by the government of the member state concerned, and not by criminal networks involved in migrant smuggling and human trafficking.

In the context of re-evaluating the situation inside Syria, a Cypriot official said, "Any re-evaluation of the situation in Syria does not necessarily mean deporting Syrian refugees to their country. Instead, Syrian refugees coming from areas that have been re-classified as safe will lose allowances, benefits and the right to work, which may discourage others who want to come to Cyprus" (Russia Today, 2024).

A European document revealed a letter from ministers of seven European countries, urging the EU bloc to review its policy with Damascus and abandon the "three no's" related to sanctions, normalization and reconstruction, in addition to the principle that "peace cannot be achieved in Syria under the Assad regime." It proposes interacting with the Arab rapprochement with Syria and returning Damascus to the Arab League, starting in mid-2023. It is known that, in April 2017, the EU Council had approved the European strategy toward Syria, which has been amended several times, as previously mentioned, and is based on the three no's: no to normalization with Damascus, no to lifting sanctions, no to rebuilding Syria, unless tangible progress is achieved in the political process, and following international resolution 2254 (Al-Sharq, 2024).

6.4. Impacts of the governance of return migration from Iraq to Syria

6.4.1. Consequences of regional return migration

A. Protection

Although the Syrian constitution and other Syrian legislation emphasize that Syrian citizens should not be deported from their country or prevented from returning to it, the implementation of these constitutional and legal guarantees does not exist on the ground. Syrian citizens always live in a state of anxiety and the fear that charges will be brought against them under various pretexts and arguments, especially if they do not belong to the prevailing regime or support its policies. Those who return to Syria have negative indicators and are required to prove their loyalty to the regime in one way or another, and are often kept under surveillance and prosecution (Syr-MNA-Micro-M). This has a negative impact on the return because returnees have to prove their innocence, that their departure from Syria was not for reasons of opposition to the Syrian regime or for political reasons, and the returnees are subjected to a security investigation after their return, whether at the border or at airports (Syr-SMH-Micro-F).

In exchange for allowing Syrian refugees to return to their homeland, the Syrian Government under the Assad regime imposed a series of demands on the international community. A presidential statement revealed that “the safe return of refugees to their towns is a priority for the state, with the necessity of securing the basic infrastructure, and the requirements for reconstruction and rehabilitation in all its forms, and supporting them with early recovery projects that enable returnees to regain their normal life cycle” (Al-Jazeera, 2024). In late 2023, Syrian Foreign Minister Faisal Al-Muqdad explained his government’s demands by saying, “The return of refugees faces difficulties due to the difficult economic and humanitarian situation imposed on the country, and for refugees to return, they need infrastructure and service facilities” (Al-Jazeera, 2024).

Syria is also a state party to several UN human rights agreements that oblige the Syrian state to protect and promote respect for human rights (Amnesty International, 2023). It appears that the country has a legal basis to protect the rights of its returning immigrant citizens according to approved international standards, but confidence in these procedures is not commensurate with the extent of legal protection on paper. Moreover, the continued transmission of information about coercive or illegal measures taken by the Syrian Government against some of its returnees has weakened confidence in it, as well as reduced the chances of voluntary return or reassurance when deciding to return.

B. Instability/Mobility

At a time when calls for the safe and voluntary return of Syrian refugees and internally displaced persons to their areas are increasing, information is emerging about government measures that increase the fear of migrants deciding to do so, especially the continued state of instability in many

regions of the country and the ongoing internal displacement crisis, the difficulty of moving between regions and even the ongoing threat of arrests, enforced disappearances and torture. Recently, decisions taken by the Syrian Government of al-Assad regime have emerged, including Decree No. 63 of 2024, which orders the seizure of the funds of hundreds of Syrians (Al-Hurra, 2024), without going through the legal system, on the grounds of combating money laundering and the funding of terrorist activities. This has caused apprehension about returning home among Syrian individuals and business owners residing outside the country due to fears of facing baseless allegations, hindering their plans to go back (SNHR, 2024).

The UNHCR reported on the situation of returning Syrians, where one returnee described how she and her two daughters were detained by government security forces for a week while trying to leave Syria for a second time, “and said that her family had to pay a bribe of US\$300 to expedite their release.” Returning women face discriminatory restrictions, particularly on the right to move freely and independently. This limitation on the freedom to move and travel within the country, as well as exiting the country, impacts the motivation for Syrians to come back home. The report details and documents cases in which women were forced to return to Syria by male family members to assess the conditions for the rest of the family’s safe and sustainable return (OHCHR, 2024).

C. Diplomacy

At the level of regional summits and meetings, these have stressed the importance of placing the voluntary and safe return of Syrian refugees to their country as a top priority. The consultative meeting of the foreign ministers of Jordan, Egypt, Iraq, Saudi Arabia and Syria, which was held at Amman in early May 2023, focused on the return of Syrians who fled their country during the war. This coincided with the wave of restoring relations with Damascus, in a step that reflects the keenness of the region’s countries for the return of Syrians to their homes. The statement announced the agreement of the participating countries’ foreign ministers that: “the Syrian Government, in coordination with the relevant UN bodies, will begin to identify the necessary needs to improve public services provided in the areas of refugee return, while clarifying the measures it will take to facilitate their return, including their inclusion in the general amnesty decrees” (MOFA, 2023).

At the Jeddah Summit held on May 19, 2023, the participating delegations, in the presence of Syrian President Bashar al-Assad, who headed his country’s delegation after 12 years of Damascus’ exclusion due to the crisis, agreed to “strengthen the appropriate conditions for the return of Syrian refugees, and preserve the unity and territorial integrity of Syria” (Kassos S., 2023). On the other hand, the Arab Ministerial Contact Committee on Syria issued the final statement of its meeting held in Cairo on August 16, 2023.⁹ This was attended by the foreign ministers of Saudi Arabia, Egypt, Jordan, Iraq, Lebanon, and the Secretary-General of the League of Arab States. The statement included following up on the implementation of the Amman Statement issued on May 1, 2023, strengthening the Arab role in resolving the Syrian crisis and addressing its political, security and humanitarian consequences, in addition to continuing

⁹ A committee formed in 2023 and composed of the foreign ministers of Syria, Jordan, Iraq, Saudi Arabia, Lebanon, Egypt, and the Secretary General of the Arab League.

dialogue in order to achieve this goal. It indicated that this would be done according to a step-by-step strategy, in line with Security Council Resolution No. 2254, preserving Syria's unity, cohesion and sovereignty, fulfilling its people's aspirations and ridding it of terrorism, as well as contributing to strengthening the appropriate conditions for the voluntary and safe return of refugees as a humanitarian priority (MOFA, 2023).

The Contact Committee and Syrian Foreign Minister in the government of al-Assad Mr. Faisal Al-Muqdad stressed the need to address the refugee crisis, with all its consequences on the Syrian people and the countries hosting them. They additionally stressed the importance of enhancing cooperation between the Syrian government and countries hosting refugees, to organize and facilitate their voluntary and safe return and end their suffering, in coordination with the relevant UN agencies, primarily the UNHCR, and following the procedures and determinants in effect in this regard, considering it a priority that must be worked on. The Syrian Minister explained the procedures and facilities taken by Syria, and referred to the cooperation and dialogue with the UNHCR, explaining the facilities provided by Damascus to the Commission to undertake its work in Syria. The Minister further stressed that the Syrian Government is continuing to take and intensify these procedures, including facilitating the opening of more offices for the UNHCR in areas of refugee return. The government periodically announces the procedures taken to facilitate their return by including them in presidential amnesty decrees, and regularly announces data on the number of returning refugees. The Syrian Government announced that it keeps to continue constructive engagement with the Commission on the issues of refugee return. Syria and Jordan continue in joint work, as stated in the Amman Declaration and, in coordination with UN agencies, to complete the return of 1,000 refugees from Jordan. The meeting further emphasized the importance of providing incentives and facilities to returning refugees, and coordination procedures with their host countries. The attendees agreed to establish a platform to register the names of refugees wishing to return, in coordination with host countries and relevant UN agencies. The Syrian Government should also provide the necessary information regarding needs in areas to which refugees will return, in addition to the need to intensify efforts to exchange kidnapped and detained persons, as well as search for those missing, in cooperation with international organizations such as the International Committee of the Red Cross (MOFA, 2023).

6.4.2. Consequences of interregional return migration

A. Protection

For many years, the Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights has documented the significant challenges and obstacles faced by Syrians in moving within their country, due to the protracted armed conflict and subsequent territorial fragmentation, which has left Syrian territory under the control of different conflict parties. Many of the Syrian former returnees interviewed by the OHCHR team confirmed the lack of respect for and implementation of the principle of non-refoulement (ACHR, 2021), for example:

1. On December 12, 2019, the Danish Immigration and Integration Ministry decided to cease providing protection to Syrian refugees, with the aim of repatriation to Syria, which was declared safe by the Danish government – especially the Damascus Governorate and other government-controlled areas. It also made a comprehensive evaluation of the refugees from government-controlled areas to see who was no longer in need of protection, and deported them from Denmark in line with the reassessment of the situation of refugees in the country. The Violations Documentation Center in Syria (VDC) recorded several refusals of requests to extend residency permits on the basis of the danger of returning to Syria.¹⁰
2. Some of the changes in the asylum policies include a reduction in the amount of assistance given to refugees, delays in family reunion processes, and the time allowed to renew residence permits to one year for approved cases without any assurance of renewal. This makes the process of assimilation into the host community very unstable due to constant fear and anxiety of being deported.
3. Practices of violence against Syrian refugees began to be noticed in Greece, at the same time as the government's decisions prohibiting the spread of information from inside refugee camps. This removes any form of check on violations that occur in these camps, including the presence of NGOs and the increasing forced repatriation of Syrian asylum seekers from Cyprus to Turkey and Lebanon.
4. On the other hand, several reports indicated that returnees were detained and interrogated by al-Assad Government security services. The Syrian Network for Human Rights recorded the detention of more than 62 returnees during 2020, all of whom were subjected to multiple abuses including torture and extrajudicial killing, thus raising questions on the safety of their life, freedom and liberty.

They also stated that movement between different parts of Syria is a major challenge and that freedom to choose one's place of residence, even within areas controlled by pro-government forces or non-State armed groups, is sometimes severely hampered. Security forces' checkpoints are numerous, not only along the so-called front lines between areas controlled by different conflict parties, but also on roads connecting cities and governorates within areas controlled by one of the conflict parties. Both men and women interviewed reported that they feared passing through checkpoints due to the harassment they faced, including the possibility of extortion of money and other personal items, arrest, detention, ill-treatment such as sexual violence, and disappearance,

¹⁰ VDC is a network of Syrian opposition activists, whose aim is to document human rights violations perpetrated since the beginning of the Syrian Civil War, including victims of the violence, detainees, and missing people.

even when they had all the necessary documents. According to interviewees, movement between areas controlled by different conflict parties may be possible primarily through the use of local smugglers after paying large sums of money. Some of these smugglers are said to operate with the approval or even coordination of elements of pro-government security forces or non-state armed groups (OHCHR, 2024).

B. Instability/Mobility

After more than a decade of violence in Syria, and the imposition of sanctions and heavy pressure on Damascus, it is clear to the Europeans – as expressed in the European Seven-Party Document – that these sanctions have begun to negatively affect the population in general, without exerting significant influence on decision-makers, and despite the introduction of useful wide-ranging humanitarian exemptions to alleviate the population’s suffering.¹¹ The Syrian Government, however, was falsely promoting the narrative that sanctions are the cause of the economic collapse and suffering in the country, ignoring its responsibility for this (Al-Sharq, 2024).

The Europeans affirm that Syria’s future is central to Europe’s security due to its proximity. They also warn that, with the continued increase in humanitarian crises, the suffering of millions and the worsening of migration flows toward Europe, it is our responsibility to cooperate with our regional partners to ensure that the EU makes every possible effort to alleviate the situation, along with creating decent living conditions. They thus plan to provide conditions for voluntary and dignified return, following international standards, as well as contribute effectively to the search for a sustainable political solution to the conflict. The European Seven-Party Document affirms that “conducting an interim review will help the EU maintain an active, practical and results-based policy in Syria” (Al-Sharq, 2024).

On this subject, the interviews conducted in the context of the research revealed a clear diagnosis of the existence of plans to move to third countries, and to try again to migrate to EU countries among the majority of Syrian refugees, especially young people or families with children, in search of a better and more stable life. Iraq was not part of their settlement plans as much as it was a primary escape to ensure obtaining money from working there, or to build clearer relationships to reach EU countries.

It seems that the Syrian situation will not improve soon and that the long duration of migration will produce long-term effects on migrants that will prevent them from thinking about returning to Syria. It will also accelerate their plans to move to countries other than Iraq, and perhaps countries outside the region (Syr-SNF-Micro-M).

C. Diplomacy

In 2023, many countries led by Saudi Arabia changed their approach toward Damascus and decided to re-admit Syria to the Arab League, as well as reopen dialogue with it. This led to a virtual stagnation in relations between the EU and Arab League, while the reality indicates that

¹¹ An initiative launched by a group of European Union members to review European policy toward Syria, especially after the Arab rapprochement with Damascus.

the political process led by the UN is faltering, as Geir Pedersen, the Secretary-General's Special Envoy, has not been able to achieve progress in the Geneva process or the Constitutional Committee. Pedersen's gradual approach does not seem to yield tangible results on the horizon, and therefore it seems that a political solution following UN Resolution 2254 is out of reach, while the humanitarian crisis is worsening day by day (Al-Sharq, 2024).

The improvement in friendly relations with some Arab countries can be understood in the context of opening new doors for Syrians to work, transfer money to their families, or facilitate obtaining a visa. The facts, however, do not seem encouraging to say that the Syrian Government of al-Assad regime in reality wants its citizens to return in this way. Some believe that it rather views Syrians abroad as an inexhaustible pool of foreign currency. On this basis, Syrian policies and their developing relations do not help improve conditions inside Syria as much as they focus on the country's future in the region. The Syrian Government's former Economy Minister Lamia Assi explained in a statement in April 2023 that daily remittances coming from abroad are estimated at 6 million dollars, equivalent to two billion dollars annually (Al-Hurra, 2024). As a result, Syrians today are more willing to try to emigrate again, even after returning to their country, because they can guarantee their safety from the Assad regime's cruelty and a decent life for their families as a result of the remittances.

Perhaps the indications contained in this research clarify the extent of the influence of the relationship between Iraq and Syria (and in particular the Syrian and Iraqi Governments, or the political and military groups in Iraq) on both countries' policies toward immigration and the protection of Syrian immigrants' rights. The great coordination between the two countries may, in certain circumstances, push a large section of Syrians in Iraq to head to different destinations, of which the EU countries are the most important.

7. Recommendations

7.1. Recommendations to the Iraqi Government and Kurdistan Regional Government

- Urge Iraq to take a clear legal position on the use of the term guest as an alternative to the term refugee for Syrians in Iraq, in order to establish clear standards of protection and ensure that this group enjoys their legal rights under national and international law.
- Adopt the principle of transparency in dealing with Syrians in Iraq by publishing information and statistics on the websites of the concerned government agencies, to help them plan to provide support and assistance to them.
- Adopt effective laws to prevent illegal immigration and confront the migrant smuggling networks that are active in Iraq to smuggle Syrians to third countries.
- Adopt effective legal systems in the fields of labor, social security and retirement for non-Iraqis.
- Spreading a culture of tolerance, building civil peace and acceptance of others, and preventing any opportunity for hate speech and xenophobia to emerge.

- Adopt the principle of voluntary return of Syrians when possible and appropriate, and if the Syrian government or fighters in areas outside government control allow them to return safely and securely.
- Work to unify and coordinate laws between the federal government and the KRG, as well as coordinate joint action in a manner consistent with human rights principles, in addition to not using return as a political pressure card, and making the humanitarian margin the main driver of return migration.

7.2. Recommendations to the upcoming Syrian Government

- Commit to and ensure full compliance with its legal and humanitarian obligations, under international humanitarian law and human rights law, toward all persons under its jurisdiction, including Syrian returnees, in particular concerning protection from any form of discrimination or abuse.
- Facilitate the return of Syrians to their home country, or settlement elsewhere if they wish to do so, in safety, security and dignity.
- Facilitate the issuance of all civil documents, such as personal IDs, housing papers, land, property and inheritance rights.

7.3. Recommendations to the international community

- Ensure the principle of non-refoulement of Syrian refugees and promote the idea of the free will or subsidized return.
- Call on the international community to come up with the right measures, along with the required help and assistance, so that the pressure on host countries is eased and return policies are facilitated.
- Strengthen the role of civil society organizations to be able to work effectively and coordinate their activities in host countries, as well as to help, support and enhance the role of the state and not to substitute it.
- To solve the refugee problem, great coordination must be carried out on several levels, and host countries must continue to allow the entry of legitimate refugees into their territories, in line with the principles of international humanitarian law and human rights law.
- Urging EU countries to assist Iraq in the issue of governance of return migration by improving its legislation on this matter, and adapting it to be consistent with international and humanitarian standards and laws.

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